

Driving Sustainable Success: Exploring the Impact of Green HRM Practices on Employee Performance in Manufacturing Industries in Kerala

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Abstract:- Green HRM is a new concept that emerged in response to the increasing awareness of environmental issues and the need for businesses to adopt sustainable practices. The main motive of the study is to explore the impact of green HRM Practices on employee performance in manufacturing industries in Kerala. . Green HR practices can applied in areas like recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, employee engagement, communication, green work practices, green development, green rewards, etc. It has been found that green HR practices can have a positive impact on employee performance in several ways.

Keywords:- Green HRM, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Green HRM is an approach to human resource management that integrates environmental considerations into HRM policies and practices. Green HRM boosts environmental sustainability by adopting human resource practices. By adopting Green HRM policies and practices, organizations can contribute to a more sustainable and environmentally responsible business model. This approach enhances and meets the expectations of stakeholders and organizations' goodwill.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the green working environment of the organization.
- To study the human resource policies and practices regarding the improvement of the employee performance of the organization.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Due to increasing the number of different types of industries, organizations need to adopt eco- friendly management. This paper mainly concentrates on the Green human resource policies and Practices of the organization, the green working environment and sustainability of the

organization, the implementation of green HRM practices, and analysis of how they affect the performance of employees.

IV. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Manufacturing industries play a pivotal role in the Indian economy. Manufacturing industries are essential drivers of innovation, economic prosperity, and societal advancement. Kerala, known for its vibrant manufacturing sector, presents a unique backdrop for examining the dynamics of Green HRM and its implications on employee performance. The study focuses on exploring the impact of Green HRM practices and employee performance in manufacturing industries in Kerala. Green HRM promotes environmental sustainability, reduces carbon footprint, and fosters a culture of eco-consciousness among employees. In the context of Kerala's manufacturing public sector industries, Green HRM involves integrating environmentally sustainable practices in the human resource management strategies of these organizations. Green HRM can applied in areas like recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, employee engagement, Green culture and communication, Policy development, etc. In Kerala, which has a strong focus on environmental conservation and sustainable development, manufacturing industries can benefit from adopting Green HRM practices to enhance their competitiveness, improve their environmental performance, and meet regulatory requirements. By integrating sustainability principles into HR processes, Kerala's manufacturing industries can contribute to the state's efforts to achieve economic growth while minimizing environmental impact.

V. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In recent years, Green HRM has emerged as a crucial strategic approach. In the realm of organizational studies, the intersection of environmental sustainability and human resource management has significant attention. In the context of manufacturing industries, understanding Green HRM initiatives and employee performance becomes paramount. This review aims to synthesize existing literature on the interplay between Green HRM initiatives and employee performance within the specific context of manufacturing

industries in Kerala.

(**Jackson et al., 2011**). Studying the relationship between HRM and the environment, researchers draw the results that HRM imparts to intensify or further improve the quality, and value of environmental performances. Emphatically, different Green HRM practices can develop willingness, inspiration, and commitment in employees to contribute their efforts, and ideas to the greening of their organization. (**Ong et al., 2022**). Green HRM practices adoption can be successfully implemented if the company encourages employee motivation and gives opportunities to the employees to participate in the company's green initiatives. This will help the organization promote green culture in every aspect of the company. (**Samola, 2022**). Indicators of green HRM such as green recruitment, green selection, green training, green development, and green compensation impact employee performance. (**Devi, 2018**). The application of green HRM practices depends upon employees' commitment. (**Jeganathan et al., 2019**). Green HRM practices avoid wastage and make better profits. (**Vijaykarthigeyan & Giriprakash, 2019**). Green HRM promotes environmental Human Resource practices. (**Shah & Soomro, 2023**). With the focus on developing country context and state context, Green HRM is very important. (**Muisyo et al., 2022**). Green innovation is a key factor that drives the success of most manufacturing firms.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted a secondary data collection strategy using previous literature studies. The secondary data involved comprehensive searches across academic databases, reputed journals, articles, and online libraries. A descriptive approach is followed to understand the “Driving sustainable success : Exploring the impact of Green HRM practices on employee performance in manufacturing industries in Kerala”.

VII. CONCLUSION

Green HRM in manufacturing industries is the integration of environmentally sustainable practices and principles in to Human Resource processes and policies. When applied to manufacturing industries in Kerala, Green HRM can have significant implications for both the organization and employee performance like environmental training and awareness, employee engagement, green employee benefits, continuous improvement and innovation etc. The integration of Green HRM practices in manufacturing industries in Kerala can contribute to enhanced employee engagement, job satisfaction, and overall well- being.

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